

Supplementary Material – THz intersubband absorption in n-type $\text{Si}_{1-x}\text{Ge}_x$ parabolic quantum wells

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FIG. S1. (Color online) Dichroic transmittance at $T=300$ K for a reference undoped sample and M-HD. From the comparison between the spectra is clear that the fringes at high energy are due to interference among multiple reflections of the beam in the waveguide cavity and they are not related to any intersubband feature.